

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

System durability report

Deliverable No.	D3.2		
Due Date	30.11.2019		
Submission Date	30.11.2019		
Deliverable Leader	SUPSI / UOM		
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	PP	Restricted to other project participants (including R4D services)	
	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the project (including R4D services)	
	CO	Confidential, only for project and the R4D services	
Status	completed		

Change log

Version ¹	Date	Amended by	Changes
0.1	27-09-2019	Daniele Strigaro	First version
0.9	29-11-2019	Ramesh Warusavitharana	Prepared excel file
1.0	30-11-2019	Daniele Strigaro	Updated and finalized content

Partners involved in the work execution

Versions	Partner Name	People involved
0.1	SUPSI	Daniele Strigaro
0.9	UoM	Ramesh Warusavitharana
1.0	SUPSI	Daniele Strigaro, Massimiliano Cannata

NOTES:

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For more information on the project 4nse, link to <http://www.4nse.ch>

¹ Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0.

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Executive summary

This report concerns the analysis of the durability of the 4nse weather stations. The presented results are useful to detect which are the hardware point of failures and how the 4nse team have reacted to solve the issues risen during the project period.

1 Introduction

The system durability is defined as the capacity of the different parts, that composed the hardware layer, to resist to the degradation. In fact, the low-cost components chosen are expected to have a shorter lifetime compared to the conventional one. However, considering the lower cost related, such analysis helps in detecting which was the most vulnerable part and if the efforts for the substitution are anyway sustainable in terms of time and costs.

2 Methods

The methodology used to get the necessary information was based on the maintenance datasheets, available for each stations, which were continuously updated every time the technicians visited the stations. The data were collected using the ODK collect mobile application trough the compilation of a form remotely sent to the server data management platform. The form guided the technicians during the maintenance as a checklist composed by steps to be performed in order to guarantee the station quality. The collected data are freely available online at the following website: <http://geoservice.ist.supsi.ch/odk/>. For further information about such procedure please refer to the deliverable 2.7 where the methodology used is well-described. Using such dataset, it was possible to derive information about each component to determine the grade of the degradation and the possible causes.

3 Results

In the annex A01, the results of the analysis are presented as an excel file. A total of 64 visits were conducted in one year (from August 2018 untill Agust 2019). In Table 1, the summary of the data present in the annex A01 are showed. The most replaced component is the BME280. This component is a sensor used to measure the humidity and the pressure which also during the calibration and testing activity showed some issues in easily getting saturated. Once the stations were deployed, the BME showed to be proned to corrosion. The battery was replaced 33 times for recharging reasons. This means it was found in a critical low level of power during the check activities, in fact only 8 times was totally replaced because it was expired. The wind speed and direction were changed due to malfunctions. Regarding the rest of the components it can be noticed that very few changes were conducted. The board was replaced 16 times, but the main reason was the availability of a new version which resolved some bugs and improved the hardware resilience of the system.

Part	Total replaced parts
Board replace	16
Battery recharge & replace	33
New battery install	8
BME replace	34
Wind speed replace	16

Wind direction replace	20
RTC replace	1
Solar pannel replace	4
Temperature sensor replace	3
SD card or logger replace	3
Solar charger	3
Solar charger & Reset circuit	4

Table 1. Total replacements for each component.

4 Conclusions

The final results showed that the most critical part was the BME280 sensor together with the wind sensor. Even if such amount of failures was not expected from what was seen during the period of the test performed on the prototype, these failures were anyway well managed thanks to the frequency of the visits for the maintenance and thanks to the automatic data quality (see deliverable 3.1) checks that helped in the detection of malfunctions.